

Exploring English Language Teaching at Dakhil Level in the Aliya Madrasas in Bangladesh

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Abstract: *In Bangladesh, a large group of students study in the Aliya madrasas that provide both religious and secular education. According to the new curriculum, the students studying at the Aliya madrasas must learn English language from Ebtedayee level (primary) and continue until Kamil (masters) level. However, the reports from BANBEIS and World Bank (2015) have revealed that the English language proficiency of the students are below the standard. Therefore, this study is an attempt to explore the English language teaching and learning approaches applied at Dakhil level in Aliya madrasas. Dakhil level is considered equivalent to S.S.C or secondary level education in Bangladesh. Data for the study was collected using a mixed method that included a questionnaire survey, interviews and focus group discussion. A total 50 teachers and 200 students from ten Aliya madrasas participated in the survey. The major findings revealed that CLT methods were not properly implemented in the Aliya madrasas at Dakhil level. Lack of adequately trained teachers, backdated syllabus, lack of necessary teaching aids, large class size and prevalence of traditional language teaching methods have been identified as the major causes for the poor teaching and learning of English language at the Aliya madrasas in Bangladesh.*

Keywords: *CLT, Aliya Madrasa, Dakhil level, ELT, NCTB, English for Today*

Introduction

In Bangladesh, English language education was introduced in madrasa education in 1971. At the beginning, unlike the English language teaching in the Bangla medium institutions where all skills of English language were emphasized though disproportionately, importance was only given on teaching reading and writing skills in English language to the students of Aliya madrasas.

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In 2012, with the last modification of the book English for Today communicative language teaching and learning was introduced at secondary level of general education system as well as in Aliya madrasas. The new English for Today series was prescribed by the National Curriculum and Textbook Board (NCTB), to promote communicative language teaching method known as CLT. Saha (2012) has stated “the textbook is developed to help the students attain competency in all four language skills, i.e., reading, writing, listening and speaking.” (English for Today, 2012) However, due to inadequate or no training and knowledge of the new approach, the teachers at Dakhil level could not implement the communicative teaching effectively in the classrooms. This book has lesson plans and learning outcomes explained and attached with each lesson. The teachers at Dakhil level are expected to teach each lesson following the prescribed lesson plan and teaching pattern.

As the communicative language teaching approach is more student oriented, it is believed to be the most motivating approach in language teaching. Rebecca Oxford (1990) states, “CLT deliberately emphasizes self-direction for the learners” (p-171). Therefore, in the present research, the researcher made a survey on the teachers who are currently teaching English language at Dakhil level to identify how much they are using CLT techniques to teach English language and to what extent students of Aliya madrasas are getting benefit from the new teaching style.

Problem Statement

In Aliya madrasas at Dakhil level, 200 marks were added recently in the syllabus for English paper I and paper II. (Dakhil syllabus-session 2019-2020). Therefore, the prescribed textbook English for Today was recommended for learning English language through communicative language teaching method. The main aim of introducing a new method of teaching English language was to enhance the communicative competence of the learners. However, after the addition of 200 marks in English language there had been large number of failing grades and significant dropouts at Dakhil level. (BANBEIS, 2017). Teachers must ensure that the communicative activities are properly practiced inside the classes as per the lesson plans.

Research Rationale

In Bangladesh, there are three different streams of education system such as, Bangla medium, English medium and madrasa education. In Aliya madrasas, the largest group of students are admitted every year due to its low cost and conservative atmosphere. However, very little research was conducted on the syllabus, curriculum and the teaching and learning in madrasas. Majority research regarding communicative language teaching was conducted on primary or secondary level students studying in the general stream or Bangla medium institutions. Therefore, the researcher endeavored to focus light on English language teaching and learning in the Aliya madrasas to identify the drawbacks and thus lessen the failing grades and dropouts from Dakhil level. The findings of the study are likely to illuminate the next course of action towards the enhancement of English teaching quality at Aliya madrasa in general, and at Dakhil level in particular.

Objectives

The objectives of the study are:

- 1) to explore the English language teaching and learning strategies at Dakhil level in the Aliya madrasa.
- 2) to examine how much the students are being benefitted with the communicative approach to language learning.

Literature Review

The literature review covers key constructs relevant to this study and the recent studies on communicative language teaching and its appropriateness in language learning [such as Hossain (2012), Haque (2008), Sultana, (2018), Mehmet (2020), Saha (2012), Oxford (1990) and Dorney, (2006) etc.

Key constructs

Communicative Competence

Noam Chomsky (1967) defined communicative competence as an ability to understand, repeat and produce new utterances or an ability to use the

language in a concrete situation. He further explained that each individual possesses an innate ability to produce grammatically correct sentences. On the other hand, Dell Hymes (1982) opined that, Chomsky's theory was sterile and explained that communicative competence enhances when communication is taught along with cultural influences. In his view, a person who acquires communicative competence acquires both knowledge and ability for language use in every type of situation. Hyme's Communicative Competence Model of CLT encompasses the competence in the following areas:

Grammatical Competence: It refers to linguistic competence where a learner is able to write correct sentences by possessing grammatical and lexical capacity.

Discourse Competence: It refers to the ability of the learners to understand and interpret individual message elements and be able to explain how meaning is represented in the entire discourse.

Strategic Competence: It refers to the coping strategies that communicators employ to initiate, terminate, maintain, repair and redirect communication.

Sociolinguistic Competence: It refers to understanding the social context in which communication takes place, including role- relationships, the shared information of the participants and the communicative purpose of their interaction.

Gardner (1985) has also spoken about communicative competence in his theory of multiple intelligence and stated that people who are strong in linguistic-verbal intelligence are likely to use words well both while writing and speaking. These individuals are typically good at writing stories, memorizing information, and reading.

To enhance the competence levels on all these four skills', psycholinguists have suggested procedures and activities to teach second language. Finocchiaro and Brumfit (1990) have suggested role-play activities, dialogue practices in the formal and informal settings, question and answer sessions among peers, topic discussions and many other engaging activities inside the classrooms. Each activity must have a specific learning outcome and teachers

must ensure that all four skills, i.e., reading, writing, speaking and listening are practiced at a time through the interactive lessons.

Motivation and Affective Filter

The factors like Motivation and Affective Filter have been found to have important impact on L2 acquisition. Advocating the importance of positive attitude in L2 acquisition, Gardner has emphasized second language motivation and considered motivation and attitude as crucial factors that help determine the level of proficiency achieved by different learners. To increase communicative competence Krashen (1986) also notes that motivation, self-confidence and anxiety in his Affective filter hypothesis as three categories of variables that play a great role in second language acquisition.

Taking the North American context in consideration, Savignon (2006) has noted that through CLT activities students engage in real communication that ultimately develop their competence level, therefore, in North America and Europe, CLT syllabus was adopted for the speakers (whose native language was not English) to teach English language to get the best results. Learners' sociolinguistic and discourse competence enhanced remarkably after ensuring proper practice of communicative language teaching.

Referring to Chinese secondary school students, Cheng's (2015) action research observed that most of the students enhanced communicative competence after the teaching strategies were modified and that reduced students' anxiety in the language classes. (pp. 705-717)

Islam's (2016) study to identify the cause of failure of the effectiveness of CLT at primary level in Bangladesh has noted that CLT is not effective at primary level in Bangladesh because teachers failed to implement it properly. Islam has further pointed out the lack of training of the teachers at primary level and their incompetence to adapt to the new method of communicative language teaching resulted in the malfunctioning of CLT at primary level.

Alam (2016) has studied to identify the challenges stakeholders face to implement CLT in Bangladesh and found lack of training, poor socioeconomic condition, large class size and mismatch between curriculum

and assessment are the main reasons behind the failure of CLT in Bangladesh. Alam's research also identified the lack of visual aids to teach English language using CLT method in the classrooms. Communicative language teaching provides opportunities for the students to be more active in the class as it is a student-centered approach to language teaching and learning. (Dorney, 2006).

Hossain's (2012) very comprehensive study on the SSC syllabus of English language has found that it includes items that may help the students practice reading and writing but not achieve communicative competence. He has pointed out some possible causes behind this inability of students to communicate in English such as the untrained teachers, uninteresting contents of English book, "students' poor performance, lacking in the teacher-student interaction and above all, some lacking in the syllabus."

Another comprehensive study by Haque (2008) on the students at Alim level in Bangladesh has focused mainly on the standard of teaching and learning English in the madrasas in Bangladesh. He has identified major drawbacks in teaching the four skills e.g., reading, writing, listening and speaking. Similar to Hossain (2012), the researcher has pointed out that "major problems lie with textbook materials, uninteresting lessons, methods of teaching, poor quality of teachers, lack of classroom facilities and teaching aids etc." Haque's research concentrated only on the problems of curriculum in madrasa at Alim (Higher Secondary) level.

Referring to the attainment of communicative competence by SSC level students, Sultana's (2018) study has observed that "students at SSC level are not motivated enough to achieve communicative competence in spite of having CLT-based syllabus" (p. 15).

As a similar syllabus is followed at Dakhil level in the Aliya madrasas, this researcher thoroughly studied Aliya madrasa's syllabus of session-2019 and session-2020 and the English teaching context there to evaluate the appropriateness and validity of the present curriculum.

A very recent study by Mehmet (2020) has noted that the secret of motivating the L2 learners is "identifying the students' motivation and then making the

lesson relevant and enjoyable” (p-62). Therefore, in the present research, the teachers’ survey mainly aimed to investigate the extent to which the L2 teachers at Dakhil level are using communicative language teaching techniques.

In a study conducted in a composite setting of general education and Aliya madrasas, Abedin (2017) has reconfirmed that the very traditional GTM (Grammar Translation Method) is still prevailing in majority of the educational institutions in Bangladesh. The present research addressed the syllabus and curriculum of English language specifically at Dakhil level and how the syllabus is being realized.

The studies mentioned above have focused, besides the theoretical aspects of communicative language teaching, on English language teaching and learning at Aliya madrasas. But the focus on English education at Aliya Madrasas is scanty and more like an overview, so lacks any in-depth insight into English teaching at Dakhil level which is an important transition point between secondary and higher level. Moreover, majority of psycholinguists believe that 12 to 15-year old second language learners that subsumes Dakhil level students possess the highest motivation to learn a second language. Therefore, in the present research, the researcher has made efforts to investigate into the English language teaching scenario at Dakhil level with special focus on how the language is being taught there and how much of the learning outcome is accomplished, in other words, how much the students are being benefitted in terms of their proficiency in English.

Conceptual Framework

The study has evolved around theories of competence drawn by Chomsky and Hymes, theory of motivation as outlined by Gardner. A brief discussion of these theories has been included in the literature review section above.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework for communicative competence of the study

The concept of communicative approach in language teaching started from the theory given by Hymes (1972) referred to as “Communicative competence”. Hymes’s theory is a further modification of Chomsky’s (1965) theory of competence, which focused mainly on the innate ability of the speakers. Instead, Hymes theory has incorporated linguistic knowledge, communication and culture that enable a learner to make meaningful communication in a speech community. Brumfit and Jonson (1983) have spoken of the seven basic functions learners must adopt while learning a second language that modified Hyme’s theory. For example, using language to get things, to control the behavior of others, to create interaction with others, to express personal feelings, to learn and to discover, to create a world of imagination and to communicate information. Widdowson (1985) has also suggested the five basic competence learners must acquire while learning second language through CLT.

Methodology

The research that was initiated in 2021 followed the research design, instruments and data collection procedure as given below:

Research Design

A survey questionnaire was used for teachers. There were also interview sessions with madrasa teachers. Six focus group discussions were conducted with the students. The researcher personally interviewed each participant and recorded and later transcribed the information.

Population and Sampling

The sample of the research included 30 teachers who have been currently in teaching English language at Dakhil level in the Aliya Madrasas and 600 Dakhil (Class IX and Class X) students from those madrasas. In order to make the sampling representative, the researcher selected the madarsas from Dhaka, Chittagong, Khulna, Rajshahi and Sylhet which abound with many madrasas. From each district, two very high standard madrasas and two madrasas of average standard were selected for data collection because large number of students come from all over Bangladesh to these high standard madrasas, as these institutions also provide lodgings and boarding facilities to both male and female students. Therefore, the researcher assumes that the data of the chosen sample represent the entire population of Aliya madrasas in Bangladesh.

Instruments

The following instruments were used to collect data for the survey.

- a) Questionnaire Survey
- b) Face to face interview
- c) Focus group discussion

The teachers' questionnaire had two parts. The first part consisted of the demographic information of the teachers including their name, educational background, duration of class time etc. In the second part, the questionnaire had items related to communicative language teaching methods. Through the questionnaire, the researcher has endeavored to find out to what extent the teachers are using communicative language teaching methods in their English language classes and how much the students are getting benefit from the new method.

Data collection Procedure

While the researcher personally collected data from each madrasa, the ethical issues, anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were explained. For the interviews, the researcher used a few lead-in structured questions and some unstructured questions for the interview schedule. Six to ten randomly selected students from each madrasa took part in the focus group discussions.

Data Analysis and Findings

While the quantitative data was analyzed using frequency distribution and descriptive statistics in SPSS, the qualitative data was analyzed manually and thematically.

Teachers' Educational background

Although many of the researchers identified the 'less qualification of teachers' as a major factor for the failure of implementing communicative language teaching properly, the researcher, for further confirmation, surveyed the qualification of the teachers who are teaching currently in the Aliya madrasas at Dakhil level.

Table 1: Educational background of the teachers

	Frequency	Percent
BA(Hons)	12	40.0
BA(Hons)+MA	5	16.7
BA(Hons)+MA+B.Ed	4	13.3
BA (Prel) +MA	9	30.0
Total	30	100.0

Table 1 shows that few teachers from Aliya Madrasas at Dakhil level have Bachelor of Education Degrees. Moreover, there are many faculties majoring in social science, history or religious studies who teach English language at Dakhil level as they have good mastery over the language. Besides, majority of the teachers joined as full-time faculty keeping incomplete their Master's degrees.

Teaching Skills

Communicative language teaching theory suggests incorporating the four skills of language i.e., reading, writing, speaking, and listening together to get the best results while teaching any lesson. Therefore, the textbook English for Today provided lesson plans that incorporate all these skills for each lesson. But the reality portrays a different picture that is reflected in the following table.

Table 2: Teachers' opinions on EFL syllabus of Aliya madrasa

Teachers opinion	Yes	No
1. Relevancy of syllabus regarding learners' proficiency	56.67%	43.43%
2. Motivational and participatory tasks and activities	55%	45%
3. Difficulty in understanding the lessons	56.67%	43.43%
4. Quality of pictures, charts ,diagrams	17%	73%
5. Cultural elements in the textbooks	31%	69%
6. Learners are bored of similar tasks	75%	25%
7. Lesson begin effectively to draw learners' attention	23%	77%
8. Lessons are flexible to adapt if necessary	44%	56%
9. Skills are presented in an integrated manner	40%	60%
10. Learners can perform the functions taught in real life	20%	80%

Summary of the Teachers' survey

Majority teachers think the syllabus is quite difficult for the students considering their level of proficiency. The analysis reveals, 56.67% teachers said that the syllabus is relevant regarding the learning outcome of the course while 43% teachers responded negatively. In the interviews also, the teachers said that Dakhil students struggle to study English for today as they do not understand many vocabularies because they have not read Standard English language books in their primary level. However, teachers are quite positive about the topic of the lessons of English for Today, as 56.67% said the lessons are "very much" in accordance of the daily lives of the students but the activities are difficult for the students to complete. 75% teachers said that learners are bored of similar activities while during interviews, 77% teachers said, the syllabus failed to create communicative atmosphere in the classroom

during the interview, while 70% teachers said the textbook was not interesting towards the students as the students are unwilling to participate in the communicative activities. 77% teachers said the textbook do not attract the attention of the students while 73.67% teachers said the texts are not suitable regarding the linguistic level of the students. During the interviews, the teachers claimed that the main obstacle to teach English using CLT methods are the large class size. Besides the teachers are always under the pressure of completion of their syllabus. In Aliya madrasas, at Dakhil level, the language teachers are very much aware and serious about teaching and writing rules of grammar in the classes. The students memorize those rules and then use them in the sentences. They follow a deductive approach to teach grammar and language in the Aliya madrasas. Dakhil level in the Aliya madrasas teach only reading and writing skills. Few male and female teachers teach speaking skill in the class. During the interview majority of the teachers opined that only twenty marks are allotted for the listening and speaking skills in the syllabus so are they not so important. Students can also achieve good grades skipping that 20 marks.

Students with speaking skills in English

Very few students at Dakhil level can speak in English fluently. Even though majority of the teachers noted that the percentage of fluent speakers in the class are little less than fifty percent, after conducting focus group discussion with the students of Aliya madrasas, the researcher identified, this percentage should be much lower. Majority students have classroom anxiety and are hesitant to use English language for practical purposes as they have fear of making errors. It may be explained that they are not habituated to speak English language inside classrooms and thus fail to speak English language fluently. During FGD (Focus group discussions) students also informed that very few speaking and listening tasks are conducted in the English language classes in Aliya madrasas, therefore they are not familiar to speak in English language.

Table 3: Percentage of students with speaking skills in English

	Frequency	Percent
Below 40%	7	23.3
50%	14	46.7
70%	9	30.0
Total	30	100.0

During the teachers' interview, the researcher discovered that the teachers at Dakhil level struggle to speak in English fluently. In the female campuses, no female teacher could speak in English properly. Majority teachers informed that the students do not understand lectures in English language therefore they frequently switch codes when students fail to understand them.

Availability and use of teaching aids

As the prescribed textbook English for Today included interactive listening and speaking activities in the lesson plan that require audiovisual facilities, the researcher tried to find out how much the teachers use visual aids in the English language classrooms at Dakhil level in the Aliya madrasahs.

Table 4: Availability of teaching aids at madrasahs

Sl. No.	Teaching -Aids	Yes	No
1.	Black-board/ White-board	100%	0%
2.	Over-head Projector	10%	90%
3.	PPT/Slideshow/Video facilities	5%	95%
4.	Audio facilities	10%	90%

Majority of Aliya madrasah teachers use only blackboards or white boards as teaching aids, and the reason for not using other modern teaching aids is non-availability of the same and that has been reflected in the table above. The high standard madrasahs provide both video and audio facilities in classrooms but the curious paradox is that, they are rarely utilized due to the teachers' lack of training needed for the use.

Application of communicative teaching strategies

Communicative language teaching is successfully realized through certain

language teaching activities such as role play, pair work, discussions and by creating opportunities for students to practice the target language. The prescribed textbook English for Today at Dakhil level includes lessons with numerous pair and group work activities. After each lesson, clear instructions and audio files are provided for the teachers, so that they make the students involve in discussions or pair works and arrange for listening activities. The graph below shows how poorly the classes are managed in the name of CLT. Lack of proper training of the teachers has been attributed for this Teaching scenario. Very few teachers currently teaching at Dakhil level could explain properly the activities they are required to practice during teaching English language in the classrooms.

Graph 1: Communicative Language Teaching Activities practiced in the class

The study has found low or no participation of the students in the class, and reasonably the result, as the graphs below explains, is that the classes become teachers centered. If the teacher talking time (TTT) is fairly longer than the students', CLT classes are likely to fail.

Graph 2: Percentage level of Teacher Talking Time

During Focus group discussions majority male and female learners at Aliya madrasas informed that in their English language classes, the stories from the textbooks, *English for Today* and the lessons from *English grammar and Composition*, have many vocabularies they do not understand and therefore they always wait for their teachers to explain the meaning in Bangla and then complete their activities. Therefore, teachers need much time to give lectures in their classes. However, CLT do not encourage lecture bases classes instead encourage learners to find out meaning of unknown vocabularies through their inference and preconceived notion.

Graph 3: Level of English language proficiency of learners

The teachers’ own assessment of their students’ proficiency level in English, as reflected in the above bar charts, represents poor realization of the learning outcome.

It is all teacher centered

One of the focal points of the interviews with the teachers was to identify how much effectively they are using communicative language teaching methods in the Aliya madrasas and the results of the interview revealed majority of the teachers labelled their teaching of English language as lecture based. The students mainly practice reading and writing activities which are also teacher dominated. The teachers fix topics to write paragraph or essays related to the textbook such as 'load-shedding' or 'pollution' and then students prepare the essays at home and submit as assignments. Teachers at Dakhil level also teach grammar rules. They teach different types of sentences, transformation of sentences, sentence connectors, and right form of verbs and tenses. It is in fact a masked reappearance of GTM (Grammar Translation Method).

In English classes, the teachers continue delivering their lessons both in Bangla and English but students with no participation remain as passive listeners. Moreover, the teachers being unable to follow the teaching guide provided by NCTB, they prepare their own lesson plans which neither meet the standard nor comply with CLT's requirements.

Students' survey and focus group discussion

The data from students' survey and focus group discussions revealed a grim picture. Whilst the teachers claimed that they practice listening and speaking skills, though in a limited scale, the students opined, "We never practice speaking and listening in the classrooms. Our lessons are reading and writing based. We always study fixed topics for paragraph writing and essays." The students think that the textbook is interesting but they do not practice any interactive activities inside the classrooms. They never participate in any debate or conversation sessions. The audio clips or video tapes are never provided along with the textbook and the teachers do not take initiative to play those in the classrooms. The most alarming discovery was to know that the students memorize fixed responses of the lessons given in "English for Today" from various guidebooks that are available in the markets and they receive quite good grades by writing those answers in their exams. The students are asked to take notes of different grammar rules from the teachers and memorize those rules to understand grammar.

Discussion

The results of the data show that majority of teachers at Dakhil level are not qualified enough to teach English language using communicative language teaching methods. Only reading and writing skills are practiced in the classrooms at Dakhil level. The lessons of the textbook *English for Today* are taught in the classes using the very traditional language teaching method (GTM) i.e. grammar translation Method. Brumfit (2000) stated that a learner might have “million English vocabularies but will fail to speak if he does not know how to put the words together”. Therefore, only making the students memorize fixed responses and grammar rules do not help them achieve communicative competence. The teachers remain busier in the classes as the classes are lecture based. There is very little room for student interaction in accordance with the lesson plans because teachers do not have training to use CLT methods. The aim for learning English language is still limited to getting pass marks or good grades. Therefore, the teachers do not take the responsibility to teach English language for practical purposes. There are un-proportionate marks distribution in Dakhil syllabus for speaking and listening skills as only twenty marks are allotted for listening and speaking skills. The teachers are unaware of the role-play or conversational activities and Aliya madrasas do not provide advanced visual aids for teaching in classrooms, therefore teachers do not get enough logistic support to practice communicative skills or to make the classes interesting. The students do not get any motivation to practice English language skills, and so to communicate in English.

Recommendations

The researcher came up with a few recommendations for the teachers, students, NCTB and madrasa board to improve English language teaching and learning in the Aliya madrasas at Dakhil level. The teachers require training to teach English language using communicative approach at Dakhil level. They need to teach speaking and listening skills as per the lesson plans. Instead of teaching grammar rules and fixed topics, teachers should engage the students in different activities and identify grammar rules from the lessons. The teachers must provide guidelines to the students as to how they can use the language for practical purposes, and for that, teachers should have training on

teaching methods and approaches. Madrasa governing body should recruit qualified teachers with English language and literature backgrounds. Teaching aids and equipment should be available in all madrasa campuses. Madrasa education board must ensure that all campuses provide the same facilities for teaching and learning. Audio cassettes, computer labs, video facility, multimedia, over-head projector, television, colorful posters and pictures need to be available along with black and white board. The NCTB needs to ensure equal marks distribution in all four skills of language learning in the syllabus for Dakhil level. The Dakhil textbook *English for Today* must have colorful illustrations to make it attractive and motivating to students. Madrasa boards must arrange for teachers training workshops for improving English language teaching in the Aliya madrasas. To reduce large number of students in each class, Dakhil classes should be divided into several sections. The textbook of Dakhil level is quite standard considering the proficiency level of the students; however, IQAC needs to ensure that the lessons are practiced with communicative language teaching method so that the learning outcome is properly conveyed.

Conclusion

Aliya Madrasas were created to upgrade madrasa learners' education and bring them towards the mainstream so that there remains no discrimination between Madrasa learners and other secular institutions' learners but at present, this system is at its deathbed. NCTB has introduced new methods of communicative language teaching and effective textbooks but without proper teaching faculties, CLT is not being implemented properly in the institutions. The present English language teaching and learning strategies at Dakhil level do not prove to be effective in teaching all four skills of a second language. Therefore, the researcher strongly believes that the findings and recommendations of this study will help the students, teachers and stakeholders find suitable ways to improve English language education in the Aliya madrasas in Bangladesh.

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Appendix 1 [Teachers' survey questionnaire]

Respondent's Background Information

Name of the respondent:
.....

Educational Background:
.....

Gender: Male Female

District:.....

Answer the following questions by putting a tick mark (✓) against the correct answer or write the correct answer in the question paper.

1. What is the duration of each English language class?
a. 30 minutes b. 40 minutes c. 45 minutes
2. Did you receive any teacher's training for teaching English language ?
a. Yes b. No

For each of the following questions select the best option that represents your answer.

Not at all a little fairly much very much

A-4 point Likert scale represents 4= Very Much, 3= fairly much, 2= a little, 1= Not at all

<i>(Appropriateness of the Textbook "English for Today" at Dakhil Level)</i>				
1. Are the contents of the textbook are enjoyable and instructive ?	4	3	2	1
2. The lessons of <i>English For Today</i> attracts the attention of the students	4	3	2	1
3. The lessons combine the four language skills (Reading, writing, speaking and listening)	4	3	2	1
4. Vocabulary and reading texts of <i>English for Today</i> are suitable for the students linguistic level	4	3	2	1
5. Some of the activities and contents are difficult for the students to understand in the textbook	4	3	2	1
6. <i>English for Today</i> is effective in enhancing communicative competence among students	4	3	2	1
7. Do you enjoy teaching English language at Dakhil level using the textbook <i>English for Today</i>	4	3	2	1

<i>(Relevancy of the syllabus of English language at Dakhil level)</i>				
1. Is the syllabus relevant regarding the learning outcome of the course?	4	3	2	1
2. Does the syllabus include objectives, which are in accordance with the daily lives of the students?	4	3	2	1
3. Does the program enable students to like learning English	4	3	2	1
4. Does the program create communicative atmosphere	4	3	2	1

<i>(Communicative language teaching activities taught in the classrooms)</i>				
1. Do you arrange for role-play activities in the language classes?	4	3	2	1
2. Do the students practice pair works/ pair discussions in the classrooms?	4	3	2	1
3. Do the students practice peer-feed back in the classes?	4	3	2	1
4. Do the students practice picture description or story telling activities?	4	3	2	1
5. Do the students practice impromptu speech presentations/ debate?	4	3	2	1
6. Are there options of fun activities, games, information-gap and puzzles in the classrooms?	4	3	2	1
7. How much do the students practice English language in the classrooms?	4	3	2	1
8. To what extent do the teachers speak in English in the classrooms?	4	3	2	1
9. To what extent do you explain grammar rules in the class	4	3	2	1

23. Which of the following needs the Dakhil syllabus meet?

Pass the exams Understand teachers' lectures Use English in practical life

Get better grades and applications Be able to use the internet Write letters

24. What percentage of students can speak in English language at Dakhil level ?

Below 40% Below 50% Below 70% above 70%

25. Which teaching aids are available in the campus?

Black/white board Over-head projector Microphones/CD player

Multimedia projector/ Video facilities

26. Do you follow a particular Teaching pattern?

a. Yes b. No

27. Do you have a fixed lesson plan to teach English language at Dakhil level from your Institution?

a. Yes b. No

28. Are you allowed to use your own teaching material in the classrooms?

a. Yes b. No

29. Who speak more and remain busy in the classroom?

a. Students b. Teachers

30. Evaluate the level of proficiency of your students in English language at Dakhil level.

Very Good Good Medium Weak
Very Weak

Appendix 2 [Interview Questions for Students]

1. How much do you use English language in the classroom?
2. In what way do you practice group work, pair works or discussions/debate in the classrooms?
3. Do you feel interest to read English for Today? Explain Why?
4. Do you think English is important for your career? If yes, explain why?

5. What is your attitude towards your English language teacher and class?
6. In what way do you learn paragraph writing in the class?
7. In what way do you practice reading in the classroom using the textbook English for Today?
8. In what way do you practice speaking and listening in the class?
9. Do the activities of the textbook English for Today help you communicate in English in the classroom?
10. What are the language activities that you practice in the classrooms?

[Interview questions for teachers]

1. What activities do the students practice in the reading classes in Aliya madrasas at Dakhil level?
2. In what way do you teach the lessons of English for Today in the classroom?
3. How do you teach paragraph writing in the classrooms at Dakhil level?
4. How do you create communicative atmosphere in the classrooms?
5. In what way do you teach completion of sentences, and listening for specific information, gap-filling activities, prepositions, articles, parts of speech?
6. In what way do you teach right form of verbs, changing sentences, voice change, change of degrees, transformation of sentences, punctuations etc.?
7. What are the challenges to teach English language using English for Today at Dakhil level in Aliya madrasas?
8. What are your suggestions to improve English language learning in Aliya madrasas?